

**THE USE OF MODERN METHODS IN THE STUDY OF PEDAGOGICAL
SCIENCES OF THE PEOPLE**

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INTRODUCTION. Modern education system for the people of pedagogical sciences teaching, students of national values they mean and enhancements for significant importance has. This article describes the people of pedagogy teaching modern methods of how to apply can about debates are.

MAIN PART. People of pedagogy — this nation of the people, history, culture, traditions and values on the basis formed education system. This science teaching, young generation of national identity and values with acquainted in an important role plays. Folk pedagogy in the teaching of modern approaches and methods of use, the learning process more effective and interesting to make to help will.

Below is the teachers in the preparation of attention to be given should be that of the main aspects is to come:

1. **Knowledge update.** Teachers people's pedagogy in the field of new knowledge and trends are constantly ravishda update they needed. Teachers in the nation pedagogical, educational methodology, and innovative approaches on seminars and treninqlarda participate can. Teachers people's pedagogy of international experience study, their lessons they can.

2. **Modern pedagogical methods.** Modern pedagogical methods of mastering the teachers of the lessons more interesting and effective to make to help will. They are the following methods of their into to be taken can:

Differential Education: Each a student is an individual approach ta'minlash, their o'worthy the specific needs and abilities are considering to get.

Multi - Dimensional Education: Interactive techniques, for example, group work, discussions and role games of your application through the students actively participate to encourage.

3. **Innovative technologies application.** Modern teaching innovative technologies in the application of, the educational process more effective and interesting to make to help will. Teachers the following out carry can:

Online Education Platform: Teachers, online resources and platforms, through lessons arrange to, students with distance from communicate to and electronic textbooks use.

Multimedia Tools: Lessons for multimedia tools, for example, presentations, videos and interactive programs application through students more visual and the audience of the material provide to.

4. Teaching skills development. Teachers professional development ensure to mentorlik and mutual experience sharing system implementation to be necessary. Experienced teachers, new teachers, guidance show and skills in increasing help they can. Teachers can improve their skills by observing each other's lessons and exchanging ideas.

People of pedagogy teaching students actively participate to motivating and them practical skills that develops various modern teaching methods and new teaching technologies of the use of this important role earned is the. Such methods and methods about below patafsil the need will take.

1. Interactive Teaching Methods

1.1. Group discussions. Group discussions, students actively participate to motivate and their thoughts share the ability to develop. Discussions during the students people's pedagogy of the basic principles, values , and traditions about their thoughts express, an opportunity to have a will. This process, critical thinking and logical analysis skills increases.

1.2. Role playing games. Role games , through students, the people of pedagogy in the context of different roles to play through learn. This method, theoretical knowledge in the practice of implementation make the opportunity to gives and social skills development provide.

2. Practical Lessons

2.1. The people's traditions and folklore of the study to. Students people's traditions and folklore of the study involved to, practical sessions through out carried. Students have their own territory in the tradition related studies take they can. This process, not only theoretical knowledge, but also practical skills in both you will develop.

2.2. Workshops. People in art - related workshops to conduct, the students for the creation ofin the opportunities it creates. Students of folk art of the various dimensions of the study the opportunity to give, for example, hand labor, music and the arts on workshops conduct. These lessons not only the practical skills to develop, but also the students in the creativity also increases.

3. Innovative Technologies For The Application Of

3.1. Online resources. Modern technology, the teaching process more effective and interesting , making it an important role plays. Teachers of online platforms and resources use through the lesson of the organization be presented

to can. This, students with distance from communicate to and electronic textbooks use the possibility of returns.

3.2. Multimedia tools. Multimedia tools, for example, videos, presentations, and interactive programs to support, lessons more interesting and makes. These through, students are more visual and the audience the material with become familiar.

4. Independent studies. Students in independent studies take go to the opportunity to give, their analytical thinking abilities in the development of an important role to have. Independent studies for the students themselves chosen the topic in more depth and learn with an opportunity to have a will. This process has the following form to be held can:

Independent Studies: Students themselves selected topics independent studies take go to the opportunity to give. This process with them their knowledge, expand, updates, learn, and their thoughts the base of the opportunity it gives.

In scientific Works, Writing: students are people of pedagogy on scientific articles or thesis write they can. This process, as well as, their scientific writing skills development to help will.

CONCLUSION. People of pedagogical sciences teaching modern methods to apply, students actively participate to motivate and their theoretical knowledge and practical skills to converting the possibility of creates. Interactive teaching, practical sessions, innovative technology and independent research through students personal and social development provides. This process, in its turn, the country's cultural heritage conservation and development service will.

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